

2nd BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign

The second BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign was developed as part of Work Package (WP) 5 - Citizen Engagement and Knowledge Transfer, under Task 5.2 - Citizen Engagement and cross-fertilisation with Lighthouse CSA's. This campaign, dedicated to raising awareness and understanding of ocean restoration activities, aimed to highlight the efforts of impactful organisations such as [SeaForester](#), [Sustainable Ocean Alliance](#), [Fauna & Flora](#), and [Sciaena](#), who are all actively involved in ocean restoration across the Atlantic basins. The event provided a meaningful platform for dialogue and collaboration between citizens and these entities, ensuring widespread access to information on various aspects of ocean restoration efforts in the Atlantic regions.

Hosted on December 1st 2023, from 13:00 to 15:00 UTC, the event adopted a hybrid format, integrating the Atlantic International Research Centre (AIR Centre)'s weekly webinar series, Networking Friday, and taking place at Hotel Baía, Cascais, Portugal. The session attracted over 20 online participants, hosted 12 in-person attendees, and is available on [YouTube](#) for those interested in reviewing the insights and discussions shared.

Following a panel presentation by the invited organisations, the session also included an interactive segment involving these organisations, in-person attendees, and online participants. The interactive session aimed to gather insights on successful citizen science initiatives and to comprehend how our target audience wishes to participate in upcoming citizen campaigns.

Please find below the detailed program.

1:00-1:05	Opening remarks , José Moutinho, Chief Business & Networking Officer at The Atlantic International Research Centre (AIR Centre)
1:05-1:15	Ice-Breaker Session with a Quiz
1:15- 2:30	Panel Presentation – Engaging Citizens in Ocean Restoration <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Ocean Restoration through Citizen Engagement - Education, advocacy and active participation, Jan Verbeek, Scientific Manager at SeaForester○ How is Sustainable Ocean Alliance Global Community contributing to restore ocean health, Eugénia Barroca, Consultant at Sustainable Ocean Alliance

- **Lessons From An Emerging Marine Protected Area Network In The Gulf Of Guinea**, Luisa Madruga, Seascapes Programme Manager at Fauna & Flora
- **Ocean, Climate and Everything in between**, Ana Matias, Climate and Pollution Policy Officer at Sciaena

Q&A moderated by José Moutinho

2:30 - 2:55

Discussion Session – Interactive Dialogue on Ocean Restoration

2:55 – 3:00

Closing Remarks